

THE ROLE OF COORDINATION ABILITIES AT THE INITIAL STAGE OF TRAINING YOUNG ROWERS

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Abstract: The article reveals the role and importance of developing of balance skills and the feeling of water when learning the technique of canoe paddling.

Keywords: Equilibrium, the feeling of water, beginner, balance, rowing, exercise on land, technique.

РОЛЬ КООРДИНАЦИОННЫХ СПОСОБНОСТЕЙ НА НАЧАЛЬНОМ ЭТАПЕ ОБУЧЕНИЯ ЮНЫХ ГРЕБЦОВ

Аннотация: В статье раскрываются роль и значимость развитие навыка равновесия и чувство воды при обучении технике гребли на каноэ.

Ключевые слова: Равновесия, чувство воды, новичок, баланс, гребной спорт, упражнение на суше, техника.

INTRODUCTION

Increasing and realizing the creative and intellectual health of the younger generation, the formation of a healthy lifestyle among children and young people, ensuring their wide involvement in physical education and sports. Due to the serious attention paid to the sport of children and adolescents in our country, a wide range of opportunities are being created for raising the younger generation physically mature, improving their health and achieving results in competitions of different sizes. In this regard, the decision of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated June 3, 2017 PQ – 3031 "on measures for the development of physical education and mass sports" is taken as the basis. In addition, the president of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Based on the decree of Mirziyoev dated March 5, 2018 "on measures to radically improve the system of Public Administration in the sphere of physical education and sports" PF – 5368, to be considered as one of the priorities for the development and popularization of physical education and sports in our Republic, especially children's sports.

RELEVANCE

No matter how much a coach dreams of immediately teaching a beginner the art of rowing as early as the first sessions, that is, the skill of being able to advance a boat through strong rowing, unfortunately, this is not possible because kayaking and canoeing are considered unstable sports equipment, and at first it is also difficult to learn how to simply sit in them. The oarsman's ability to maintain balance is similar to the art of Medicine. In kayakers and canoeists, the feeling of balance should not be less. After all, an athlete often performs various "halaky" (strong wave, opposite or lateral wind, etc.) during training and competitions. k.) are subject to factors. There are many cases when athletes regularly lose when the weather changes, showing high results in good weather. Such paddlers can be very well prepared in terms of functionality, a lot of Labor can be spent on them over the years, but it is impossible to train such a paddler anew and turn him into a high-class athlete.

Poor balance retention in the boat is a very common technical error. In particular, a few meters before becoming the champion of the country can be remembered for rowers who flew out of the boat.

It is necessary that the new oarsman learns to be able to feel the water and, most importantly, to correctly perform strong rowing movements at the level of being able to feel the muscles. It is a sad situation to watch a paddler rowing under the excitement, increasing the high tempo, which is not related to the speed of the boat moving forward. The experienced gaze of the coach immediately determines that the athlete cannot "hiss" the water and, without using it to advance the boat, simply bursts the water with a paddle. Such a rowing boat will stand in the same place as if an anchor was thrown. Research described in the scientific and methodological literature is carried out on paddlers who reliably occupy more balance as well as the technique of rowing movements. However, young athletes who come to the sport of rowing have very little work dedicated to the formation, mastering and rapid development of balance, rowing techniques and the art of boat control. Most popular experts in rowing on this issue say that young rowers need to first learn the technique of rowing and the mastery of their own balance on land. However, how, where, what and in what way to teach? These questions have not been answered by scientists, therefore, it is very important and relevant for young rowers to delve into the existing problems at the initial comfort stage. [3.27,4.37]

Aim of the work. To reveal how it is necessary to improve the perception of water and the development of balance skills in the sport of rowing.

To achieve the aim, we put the following tasks in front of us:

1. Research and taxing literature on the topic.
2. To indicate the factors that affect balance in the sport of rowing.
3. Determination of the sequence of development of water perception and balance skills.
4. Poll among coaches.
5. Conclusion.

RESEARCH RESULTS

Mistakes made at the beginning of Education will certainly lead to sad results. Therefore, we wanted to share special methods aimed at developing a sense of water and balance, as well as to teach paddlers to take a more rational approach to improving their technical skills.

The sense of balance is due to the development of the **vestibular** apparatus, mental stability, complex conditions in the aquatic environment – a strong fear of turbidity in waves and wind. Such factors limit movements and cause irritability. Balance is closely related to another factor - the feeling of water: a subtle feeling of water density through the muscle (especially pronounced when catching water in the initial phase of rowing). Not losing contact with the innate or acquired ability associated with "water hiss" under any circumstances can allow you to achieve a higher speed by removing physical strength to a minimum (more precisely, optimal) level.

Feeling water is a generic term for the oarsman. Muscle structure as well as the boat's rhythmicity in different weather conditions, the integrity of the "rowing-rowing-boat" system, the level of rowing, the depth of the pond, the density and temperature of the water, the structure and weight of the current, kayak or canoe, the OAR's position in the boat, the ability to persevere in complex conditions, calmness, monandness to rhythm, amplitude, technique, tactical skill, functional readiness, – all this affects the perception of water.

Balance and the feeling of water provide the basis for the ability to enter rowing with all its might, to make the most numerous muscles travelable, to effectively coordinate their mutual movement.

The feeling of water and Balance serves as the basis for further improving the technical skills of the athlete and ultimately determines the effectiveness necessary from the first moments of sports activity.

We are sure that at least 50% of the elements of the rowing technique can be mastered on the shore, especially at the beginning of training. An individual approach is essential in this. It is important not to scare the novice with the difficulties of maintaining balance on the boat. Often, coaches use a simple method, which is to shoot a new athlete into a boat, repeatedly choking him, and watching him pour water inside the kayak to the shore, sit on it and fall back into the water a few meters later. Water, on the other hand, is often cold, as young athletes are sorted in late autumn or early spring. Practitioners experience fear of water, resulting in more than half of the students in the rowing sector dropping out of the sport.[1.18,5.67]

Therefore, it is necessary to prepare new athletes from the very beginning: to perform balance training, work on simulators, and only then go to the water. In the educational process, it is necessary to follow the sequence and patience, apply a variety of methods and devices in training. The rowing base should have enough tools. You can create almost all the necessary tools and gadgets with your own lake: training soles, rocking boards, catamarans, multi-seat canoeing.

It should be noted that early involvement of children under the normatives program intended for adults leads to serious technical errors. First it is necessary to apply exercises that are specifically aimed at improving all components of the technique from the head. In this case, it is necessary to bring exercises through an individual approach to execution in an automatic position, as well as not to forget about exercises for peace of mind. Once a motion stereotype is formed later, it may not be possible to correct the defects.

The work on the development of balance, water perception skills is closely related to other issues related to the technical skill of the oarsman, which, together with all other sections of training, must be carried out in complex, taken into account in promising and current planning.

Hence, the development of balance and water sensation skills will take place in the sequence below:

- I. To explain the need for the oarsman to master these qualities.
- II. Mastering the imitation of the technique of rowing on land.
- III. Mastering the skills of balance on the floor using a special trainer and jumpers.
- IV. Mastering the initial skills of rowing on the left.
- V. Rowing on boats with a balancing device.
- VI. In complex weather conditions (wave, wind, etc.k.) to practice specifically.

We decided to conduct a small experiment in the sport of rowing in order to see in practice how much the role of water perception and the development of balance skills is played and in what way the coaches adhere to the sequence of its development. We conducted a survey of coaches who train in rowing sports in children's and youth sport schools located in area, Tashkent and Tashkent region. The survey is made up of questions about the role of balance qualifications in water perception in rowing sports and the sequence of their development. 30 people coaches took part in the experiment. In the process of the survey, 100% of coaches noted that in the sport of rowing, especially in the initial period of preparation, water hiss and balance significance are earned. Also, all coaches mentioned that the sequence of development of balance skills is

purposeful and in the right order. However, it was revealed that coaches are in trouble when implementing certain items in the sequence. 56,6% (17) there is no special sol at the rowing base where the coach is working. Accordingly, they will not be able to qualitatively conduct activities related to water fogging. 79.9% (24) coaches do not have special trainers and jumpsuits that develop balance skills at hand. This is evidenced by the fact that training by these coaches, aimed at developing balance and coordination qualities on land, is carried out at extremely low efficiency. It was revealed that all coaches (100%) in other points in the balance qualification development sequence would be able to conduct the training at a higher level. [1.12,2.32]

As a result of the survey, we found that in the sport of competitive rowing, especially in the initial period of preparation, water perception and balance qualification significance is acquired, and in its development, the sequence identified from our side is desirable. There are enough problems in the development of these skills and competencies before the coaches.

CONCLUSION

1. Proper training in balance and water sensation skills speeds up the mastery of the basics of rowing techniques by athletes, allowing them to significantly reduce the number of participants in the initial training groups. 2. The development of water perception and balance skills on land requires the trainer to use special trainers and jumpers, unconventional methods and tools. Unconventional methods and tools used in the development of the balance of young rowers allow the formation and development of the balance sheet, coordination capabilities, balance qualifications and vestibular apparatus of those involved, which allows the reliable performance of the rowing directly on the boat, achieving a stable balance in a short time without any permissible obstacles.

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